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Pastoral Care Intervention for Drug Addiction in the Present Nigerian Society

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Abstract

This paper examined pastoral care intervention for drug addiction in the Nigerian society, claiming that the widespread use of addictive substances is visible around nooks and crannies where people easily get access to drugs and other highly intoxicating drinks. Some hawkers also go round the towns and villages to sell medications and alcoholic drinks without any checks. Consequently, drug addiction is becoming a widespread phenomenon with serious challenges in Nigerian society. The paper submitted that apart from the mental health-related illnesses of addiction on addicted individuals, their families, communities, and the nation at large suffer from the challenges of addiction. The objective of this paper is to explore the concept of drug addiction, examine some factors responsible for the addiction, identify some of the effects, and explain how pastoral care could be used and integrated into other modes of care for the holistic recovery of addicts. The paper followed a descriptive research design and based its position on scholars' and professionals' opinions on the subject of drug addiction and pastoral care intervention, submitting that treatment of addiction requires teamwork among all caregivers and proposing practical pastoral care approaches to

help addicts live a meaningful life and become a reliable member of society.

Keywords: Pastoral Care, Drug, Addiction, Caregivers, Nigerian Society

Introduction

The widespread and non-medical use of psychoactive substances, including some over-the-counter (OTC) medicines and alcohol, has become a serious pastoral and public-health concern in Nigeria. OTC drugs are medicines sold directly to consumers without a prescription. These drugs are supposed to be used to manage self-safety-diagnosed, minor ailments, like cold and catarrh, pains, and allergies. These medications are regulated by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to ensure safety and effectiveness when used according to the label instructions (National Institute on Drug Abuse, NIDA, 2017). As good as this decision and regulation may be, the writer observed that abuse of over-the-counter drugs is common among teenagers and young adults. This could be because those medications are readily available in their homes and friends' medicine cabinets.

The present Nigerian society is flooded with roadside shops, pharmacies, grocery stores, and other retail locations. Some hawkers also go round the towns and villages to sell medications and alcoholic drinks without any checks. This accessibility opens people with and without addiction tendencies to the danger of abuse and addiction. Addiction is a primary, chronic disease of the brain reward, motivation, memory and related circuitry. Any dysfunction in these circuits leads to biological, psychological, social, and spiritual abnormalities. The general behaviour of some individuals in Nigerian society today indicates that they are under the influence of drugs.

The writer, as a counselling psychologist, is privileged to work with other therapists for one-on-one therapeutic intervention of students with questionable characters, some of whom are traced to the influence of drug use. There was a case of a student who defecated on the floor inside the toilet, which has neat water closet facilities. This act was discovered when the next user entered the toilet and saw how the first user defecated in a triangular form on the floor. To the panel's surprise, the boy said he only wanted to create fun. The student, along with a few others, was later expelled from school due to drug use. It is obvious that addiction of any kind affects human behaviour, which could lead to the violation of some moral standards either at home or in the community. Many homes have been

disorganised, relationships cut off, opportunities lost, and goals unachieved because of ugly and unresolved issues of addiction. Addiction has caused many able and skilful men and women to feel unfulfilled, and jeopardises individual overall well-being, relationships, and quality of life.

Having considered the prevalence of addiction in the present Nigerian society, it was also observed that there is insufficient collaboration between the pastoral caregivers and health caregivers in tackling addiction and providing recovery. Therefore, the quick intervention of all and sundry, especially pastoral caregivers, is required to address and prevent the problems. Pastoral caregivers, in most cases, are privileged to know about addictive behaviour before any other professional caregivers. This is because parents, guardians, and relatives report and seek first the help of pastors even before the addicts are taken to the hospital for medical attention.

There are several referral cases of drug-influenced maladaptive behaviours from the chaplaincy units of some institutions to medical practitioners for clinical intervention. The writer observed that the consequences of getting addicted to drugs, in most cases, usually start in a small stage and gradually become a severe challenge. The aftermath of drug addiction, particularly on mental health, is so challenging and disheartening. This, therefore, calls for proactive caregivers' intervention to ensure positive changes and all-inclusive healing of the addict and their significant others.

Although addiction is widely discussed in public-health literature, less attention has been paid to how pastoral caregivers in Nigerian Christian settings can contribute ethically and collaboratively to recovery. This article offers a conceptual framework for pastoral care in response to that question. The paper deals with the concept of drug addiction, causes, and consequences of drug addiction, as well as pastoral care intervention in drug addiction. This interplay of moral weakness, biological vulnerability, and spiritual brokenness necessitates an integrative response.

Overview of Drug Addiction

Historically, addiction was viewed primarily as a moral failure because it collapses a theological interpretation into a universal historical account. Starting from the temperance movement of the 19th century, addiction reflected a moral framing, particularly toward alcohol consumption and other illegal substances. In contemporary time, addiction is viewed as an interplay of moral weakness, biological vulnerability, and spiritual

brokenness that necessitates an integrative response which hijacks the brain circuits that govern reward, motivation, and self-control. However, advances in neuroscience shifted the paradigm, recognising addiction as a brain disease involving reward pathways (Volkow & Koob, 2015).

Addiction is characterised by an inability to abstain consistently, impairment in behavioural control, and craving, diminished recognition of significant problems with one's behaviours and interpersonal relationships, and a dysfunctional emotional response. The above assertion can be buttressed by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) position that views addiction as a problematic pattern of substance use, leading to clinically significant impairment or distress which the victims cannot do without despite the damages (APA, 2017).

Like other chronic diseases, addiction often involves cycles of relapse and remission. Without treatment or engagement in recovery activities, addiction is progressive and can result in disability or premature death. Addiction also affects neurotransmission and interactions between cortical and hippocampal circuits and brain reward structures, such that the memory of previous exposures to rewards (such as food, sex, alcohol and other drugs) leads to a biological and behavioural response to external cues, in turn triggering craving and/or engagement in addictive behaviours (APA, 2017).

The prevalence of drug abuse and addiction in Nigeria by geopolitical zones shows: 1.5 million which is 10 percent in the North Central; 1.55 million which 13.8 percent in the South East; 2.09 million which is 13.6 percent in the North East; 2.12 million which is 16.6 percent in the South South; 3 million which is 12 percent in the North West; and 4.38 million which is 22.4 percent in the South West (Alabi & Adewole-Tambe, 2021). The statistics show that drug addiction in Nigeria is worrisome and should be seriously addressed by the government at all levels and other necessary stakeholders for a better future for Nigeria.

Various research by experts and relevant national and international bodies have consistently discovered and exposed the dangerously rising cases of drug use in Nigeria despite the damaging outcomes of violent crimes, health complications, and abuses. As stated by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), "all over the world, many Nigerian adolescents no longer see the harmful effects of cannabis despite its biting consequences" (Alabi & Adewole-Tambe, 2021).

Drug addiction, according to Morh & Tasman (2011), is a behavioural pattern of drug use, characterised by overwhelming drug involvement which manifests in different forms: by yearning to continue taking drugs and getting them by all means (WHO, 2018). Drug addiction crisis has become a world concern as it cuts across all spheres of life and ruins valuable lives, especially among youth. Afunlehin (2019) explains drug addiction as an attempt to use any substance to the point that it brings damage to the user's health, work, education, personal relationships, judgment, and jeopardises their ability to cope with life (Afunlehin, 2019).

Drug addiction is a state of psychic dependence on a drug, arising in a person following administration of that drug on a periodic or continuous basis (Eddy, 1965, pp. 36-38). It manifests as a compulsive cycle, where the victim persistently engages in harmful behaviours despite desiring change. The interaction between biological vulnerability and spiritual detachment, an outcome of addiction, requires a multidimensional and proactive response. Miller & Carroll (2011) submit that addiction cannot be reduced to moral failure, nor should it be understood solely as a medical condition. Instead, it is assumed as a biological, psychological, and social-spiritual disorder (biopsychosocial-spiritual disorder) that requires a holistic perspective in human beings (Miller & Carroll, 2011:168).

In the view of Oyedele (2001), some of the characteristic symptoms of addiction include craving, compulsion, intolerance, withdrawal, denial, risk behaviours, and loss of control. Addiction is identified with damaging, destructive and killing features (Oyedele, 2001). Addiction is a bondage of the mind to the rule and activities of a substance, which then becomes the centre of life, defending itself from the truth so that even the occurrence of the bad consequences does not bring repentance, and leading to further estrangement from God. However, some people are habituated to a purposeful use of some drugs or treatment. For instance, the regular use of water therapy and medication for health reasons is purposeful, healthy, and beneficial to the body. These cannot be classified as an addiction.

Characteristics Symptoms of Addiction

The characteristic symptoms of addiction are explained in the ABCD and E acronyms of A=Abstinence, B= Behaviour, C= Craving, D= Diminished and E= Emotion. The ABCDE explains the characteristic symptoms of addiction.

Inability to Consistently **Abstain**: Drug addiction is a chronic disease characterised by drug seeking and use that is compulsive, or difficult to control, despite harmful consequences. Brain changes that occur over time with drug use challenge an addicted person's self-control and interfere with their ability to resist intense urges to take drugs.

Impairment in **Behavioral** Control: This is a reduction in the ability to regulate impulses, emotions, and actions, often leading to impulsive, reckless, or compulsive behaviours that violate social norms or ignore negative consequences. It is a core feature of various psychiatric disorders, addiction, and neurodevelopmental conditions.

Craving, or Increased "Hunger" for Drugs or Rewarding Experiences: This is a central defining symptom of addiction (substance use disorder) and behavioural addictions. It represents an intense, often uncontrollable, desire or urge to engage in a behaviour or consume a substance to achieve pleasure or relieve stress.

Diminished Recognition of Significant Problems with One's Behaviours and Interpersonal Relationships: This is a core feature of addiction as defined by the American Society of Addiction Medicine (ASAM). It refers to a profound lack of insight or awareness regarding how one's actions negatively affect their life, work, and relationships. This state represents a brain-behavioural dysfunction, often leaving the individual unable to recognise that their behaviour is problematic, even when the consequences are severe.

A Dysfunctional **Emotional** Response: an inability to manage or regulate emotions effectively, resulting in excessive reactions that are inappropriate to the context or damaging to oneself and others. It is often referred to as emotional dysfunction, where the intensity and quality of emotions (like fear, anger, or sadness) do not align with the triggering event.

Like other chronic diseases, addiction often involves cycles of relapse and remission. Without treatment or engagement in recovery activities, addiction is progressive and can result in disability or premature death.

Some Responsible Factors of Addiction in Nigeria

There are various factors contributing to the problem of addiction, particularly drug addiction, in Nigeria. Some of these factors are explained under this heading.

Genetic Factors: These account for about half of the likelihood that an individual will develop addiction. Environmental factors interact with the

person's biology and affect the extent to which genetic factors exert their influence. Resiliencies the individual acquires (through parenting or later life experiences) can affect the extent to which genetic predispositions lead to the behavioural and other manifestations of addiction. Culture also plays a role in how addiction becomes actualised in persons with biological vulnerabilities to the development of addiction.

Findings from Murray & Hampton (2025) revealed that children of addicted parents are more vulnerable and likely to become addicts later in life. This is not in all cases, but it is a factor responsible for the prevalence of drug abuse and addiction in Nigeria. Genetic predisposition, according to NIDA, accounts for 40–60 per cent of addiction vulnerability (NIDA, 2020). Parents should be conscious of their lifestyles and what they do in the presence of their children. Parental lifestyle can strongly influence the present and future lifestyle of their children.

Psychological Factor: Addiction is a complex, chronic condition rooted in a combination of biological, environmental, and crucially psychological factors. Psychologically, addiction often serves as a maladaptive coping mechanism for underlying emotional pain, trauma, or mental health disorders, rather than just a pursuit of pleasure. Substance abuse and addiction can be related to an individual's psychological factors, such as escape from reality, depression, anxiety disorders, PTSD and trauma, sensation seeking, cognitive distortions, boredom and the like (Cleveland Clinic).

Similarly, Adeniyi (2005), posits that drug addiction affects the brain, leading to co-occurring disorders like depression and anxiety, linking self-worth to achievements, leading to self-criticism, and causing memory loss. Personality traits such as impulsivity, acting without forethought, stress coping deficits, and trauma (Adeniyi, 2005, pp. 92-93). The above submissions from international and national research could be admitted as valid proofs that psychological distortion and ineffectiveness could fertilise and trigger addiction.

Environmental Factors: Media veneration and advertisement colouration of some addictive substances lure and entice some youth into making a first attempt in taking the advertised substance. Adeola (2020) submits that it is an indisputable fact that addiction to cigarettes starts from a stick; addiction to football starts from a watch; sex addiction begins with just one experience, addiction to alcohol starts from one glass and addiction to drugs

starts from a dosage. He concludes that addiction is a typical 'health cankerworm,' which, in most cases, starts in a little way but aggravates into an acute stage (Adeola, 2020, p. 1).

Also, the influence of media advertisements of addictive substances on the prevalence of addiction, which further normalises harmful patterns in current Nigerian society, cannot be underestimated. Afunlehin (2019), in his view, echoes that the voluntary act of taking drugs, craving, advertisement and movies are some of the roots of drug addiction (18). In other words, cultural norms that are favourable to drug use, traditional festivities, peer influence, and economic challenges are blameworthy.

Consequences of Drug Addiction

In addition, there is a significant impairment in executive functioning, which manifests in problems with perception, learning, impulse control, compulsivity, and judgment. People with addiction often manifest a lower readiness to change their dysfunctional behaviours despite mounting concerns expressed by significant others in their lives, and display an apparent lack of appreciation of the magnitude of cumulative problems and complications. Accidental death and motor accidents are the two dangers the author mentioned as problems of drug abuse and addiction. Drug addiction could also lead to some severe illnesses such as stroke, kidney problems, liver problems, blindness, numbness, psychosis, and a few others (Research Gate, 2023). Specific areas of effect are:

Mental and Physical Effects: People with drug addiction are prone to chronic diseases and organ damage. Vital organs like the brain, chemical systems and circuits, and the body's immune systems are weakened, and increase in mortality risk (WHO, 2021). Brain imaging studies of drug addiction suggest that addicted individuals show changes in areas of the brain that are critical to judgment, decision making, learning and memory, and behaviour control. Physically, drug addiction could affect the internal organs, leading to lung and kidney cancer, heart attack, nausea, stroke, impotence, among others (University of Pittsburgh Medical Centre).

Physiological Effects: Drug addiction harms the physical appearance of the addicts. The victims experience constant fever, slurred speech, red eyes, body shivering, loss of weight, impaired attention, injuries that can negatively change their life and physical structure, and untimely death (Fareo, 2012, p. 94). Psychologically, addiction often coexists with mood

disorders. “Persistent drug use and substance use disorders alter brain chemistry, diminishing emotional regulation and worsening underlying mental health issues” (UNODC, 2018). Drug addiction suppresses the cerebral cortex and leads to memory failure, causing the addicts to be mentally deranged and emotionally distressed. Marijuana and other hard drugs lead to impaired performance on a task that involves several steps. Drug addiction intoxication affects the brain, causing a reduction in self-awareness, impaired judgment, reasoning, and general cognition (UNODC, 2018).

Social Effects: Drug addiction not only affects individuals, but it extends to the family, friends, teachers and other members in the community. An addicted person sometimes becomes moody, hurt, and aggressive. This can lead to strained relationships, mistrust, disrespect to authority, withdrawal, isolation and other social issues like incarceration and damaged relationships (Adeniyi, 2005, p. 104). Drug addiction could cause behavioural disorders, which may lead to an inability to relate well with family members, community, or observe their own psychological state in relation to things that transcend their daily experience.

Spiritual Effects: The interaction of spirituality with drug addiction is a complex phenomenon. As posited by Kurtz (1992), drug addiction affects one’s spiritual life, affecting their relationship with people around and disconnection with God, resulting in spiritual stagnation and probably affecting one's existential purposes. Romans 6:16 refers to addiction as slavery that gives room for Spiritual malady (Kurtz, 1992, pp. 123-135).

Financial/Economic Effects: The financial effects of addiction, outlined by Kurtz, include difficulty in securing an appointment, which could lead to financial challenges, economic hardships such as bankruptcy, and pleading for money all around. This implies that drug addiction affects individuals in different parameters: physically, physiologically, and psychologically, socially, academically and spiritually. Families and friends of the addicted bear significant emotional and economic hardship.

Pastoral Care Intervention with Drug Addicts

Pastoral care for drug addiction provides a spiritual safety net, focusing on healing, sustaining, educating, guiding, and reconciling. Pastoral care intervention for drug addicts calls for a comprehensive approach which addresses the holistic aspects of an individual's ordeals towards recovery

through unconditional love, non-judgmental listening, and spiritual accountability. Fundamentally, pastoral care is pastoral because it is rooted in the scriptures. However, it gives room for science, medicine, culture and psychological theories. It is eclectic in nature. Therefore, pastoral caregivers are saddled with the responsibility of shaping people's lives.

Pastoral care of an addict should be multi-dimensional. This requires professionalism and teamwork. It involves a holistic, spiritual, and supportive approach designed to facilitate recovery, healing, and reintegration. Some of the approaches are:

Active Listening and Empathy: Every addict has a story to tell, but who is ready to listen? The starting point of healing for an addict is to listen actively and compassionately to them. Active listening is one of the basic skills every pastoral counsellor should possess. In listening to an addict, one does not need to be nervous or judgmental, but rather to be empathic and pay attention to both verbal and non-verbal expressions of the addict. According to Ayankeye, active listening is reflective listening. It is a skill for deeper therapeutic relationships, which can also facilitate positive behaviour change (Ayankeye, 2013, p. 12).

Active listening communicates to addicts that someone cares about them, that their lives matter, and that they are as important as others. When caregivers actively listen to them, it builds trust, respect and disregards their helpless, hopeless and dependent situations. This, in turn, gives them a new picture of themselves as people with power and wisdom who, when assisted, are capable of dealing with their problems. In Carl Rogers' view, active listening is accurate empathy or understanding. Empathic understanding is the ability of an individual to detect, recognise, feel and describe the private world or lifestyle of the addicts and accurately, with love and sincerity, communicate the experience, thoughts and feelings back to them. Empathic understanding makes addicts feel accepted and comfortable, trust the caregiver, and open their minds to receive guidance and counselling (Rogers, 1957, p. 102).

Crisis Intervention Counselling: Human nature requires counselling. Humans are complex beings who bear mental burdens, stressful feelings, emotional disturbances, painful encounters, traumas, and suffering; hence, they require experiential support and assistance for healthy survival or control in many situations. Crisis intervention counselling is relevant to any existential catastrophe one is passing through. Quitting addictive behaviour

is not easy, as many addicts have tried several times without success. The experience of relapse causes psychological torture, self-hatred, failure, and emotional trauma.

Crisis intervention counselling carried out pastorally is considered appropriate in this situation by this writer. These include prayer, deliverance where it is necessary, God-talk therapy, helping the addict to read some faith-based expository books, learning some musical instruments of their choice to engage them positively, thus preventing relapse, and counselling. It is an appropriate therapeutic process capable of charging the soul, challenging the mind, and changing behaviour. Its eclectic approach helps to address addiction holistically from clinical, psychological, cultural, and biblical viewpoints. Counselling that is carried out pastorally, according to Enyioha and Ogundipe:

It is the power that quickens liveliness in man, and it serves as the illuminator that brightens the mind about existential defects. It is the silent motivator towards the reactivation of personality and the life wire that allows for pragmatic normalcy in living. Therefore, pastoral functional counselling serves as the role-roller that moves the mind towards the realisation of an alternative direction. It serves as an exposure of reality amid confusion. Also, it serves as a persuader of personality in decision-making, and a soft dispenser of sustainable values that keep life-relationship resourceful, relevant, responsible, and reliable (Enyioha & Ogundipe, 2019, p. 122).

Pastoral care is holistic in nature. It positively affects the spirit, soul, and body, providing healing, guidance, knowledge, sustenance, and reconciliation in appropriate situations.

The Use of Prayer: The Bible teaches that the effectual fervent prayer of a righteous man availeth much (James 5:16, KJV). Trouble and prayer are closely related because prayer is of great value in times of trouble. Crisis draws people to God, but prayer is the voice of man before God. All addicts need prayers; they should be encouraged to pray for themselves as other people pray for them. "Wise is he in the day of trouble who knows his real source of strength and who fails not to pray" (Adeola, 2021, p. 45). Prayer honours God. It settles one's case by faith, which manifests in a real, true and actual sense.

Building a Community and Accountability Group: Building a community in this context means raising a group of people who are ready to work

together to achieve a common goal. Abioye (2025) posits that building a community that nurtures the recovery of an addict with all necessary support is pivotal in addiction treatment. This helps the addicts to fellowship with the right people whose focus is to help them come out of their addictive behaviours. The presence of the community encourages the addict to take responsibility for their behaviours and choices.

Creating an accountability group is also important in addiction treatment. The accountability group works together, watches over one another, and reminds itself of the group's rules, guidelines, and vision. This approach allows all addicts to be closely monitored. Having a community will help the therapist group the addicts into their areas of vocational and recreational interest. Addicts are easily engaged in groups, given assignments, and set a time frame to deliver. When addicts make commitments, and there is an accountability group, they become responsible and motivated to work hard to achieve their goals in a healthy, sober, and cordial relationship with their peer group (Abioye, 2025, p. 8).

Building a Relational Support Network: Relationships are essential in human existence. By nature, humans are meant to relate with God and with one another. Building walls of relationship for the addicts helps them to live a meaningful life. Walls of good people and cordial relationships influence one's thoughts and actions. Therapists or pastoral caregivers with relationship problems view people around them as the problem. This makes their intervention processes a failure. Every pastoral care therapeutic process is relationship-based.

Building walls of relationship for addicts creates a strong family bond, cultivates a positive mindset, helps them recognise their values, worth, and importance, and helps them discover how much they are loved. This helps them appreciate and embrace the beauty of family and work, making the family proud. Walls of relationship provide a family structure where every addict enjoys resources, support, guidance and quality time with any of the family members. This family relationship generates a positive atmosphere, through their influences, for the addicts to live a meaningful life. This includes how they dress, greet others, participate in age-related activities or programs, and display humility and wisdom (Madoghwe, 2025, p. 34).

Timely and Appropriate Referral: Referral is another way of providing care for an addict. Referral is the purposive transfer of a client's or patient's case to another helper for more detailed investigation and professional

intervention. Timely and appropriate referral is an indispensable skill for all pastoral caregivers. Referrals are good and helpful, but when they are too late or done inappropriately, the outcome can be frustrating and hazardous. A pastoral caregiver should not waste time or wait until it is too late to seek the help of other professionals, especially in the case of addiction, through referral to appropriate channels.

In most cases, pastors are the first point of contact for a church member facing a dilemma. This does not make the pastor "Mr Know-All", but rather affords him the privilege of providing solace and support before other necessary steps are taken. Cases of drug addiction should be timely referred to medical personnel because the treatment of an addict is beyond pastoral training alone, though pastoral counselling has its place in the comprehensive package for addiction treatment. Ethically, referrals should be made with the consent of the addicts and their family members, especially in the case of minors who are still under parental guidance, and there must be respect for boundaries and confidentiality. These calls for pastoral caregivers, psychiatrists, psychotherapists, family members, and significant others to work together as a team. As stated by Ayankeye (2013), since it is expedient that a pastoral counsellor should be a person of prayer, referral is essential in the case of drug addiction for de-intoxication and re-orientation in a psychiatric or medical hospital (20).

Conclusion

This paper examines pastoral caregivers' response to drug addiction in present Nigerian society as it explains the concept of drug addiction, factors responsible and consequences of addiction in present Nigerian society. Some of the root causes are biological, psychological, and social, with multiple psychological, social, economic, physical and spiritual effects. The article is specifically on pastoral care intervention that could be blended with medical intervention for effective recovery of drug addicts. Some of the pastoral care approaches that help in engagement with the addicts, assessment of the issue, spiritual and family support, and referral are specifically explained to help the addict recover and become a responsible person contributing to the growth of society. Addiction treatment requires a holistic approach that weaves spiritual, emotional and psychological supports together, a facts for all pastoral caregivers to take note. The article is limited to the professional coverage of pastoral caregivers, and not clinical intervention. However, it

emphasizes collaborative efforts of all stakeholders (Medical practitioners, psychotherapists, pastoral caregivers, social workers, family members) in addiction treatment.

References

- Abioye, M. O. (2025). "The Role of Pastoral Care in Supporting Individuals Struggling with Nicotine Addiction." *Impact International Journals and Publications*. Vol. 1, Issue 3, pp.77-87.
- Adeniyi, E. O. (2005) "Alcohol and Drug Dependence among Nigerian Students: A Threat to Nigerian Educational Development and Healthy Living," *Oro Journal of Educational and Technological Studies*, 3(1), 89–99.
- Adeola, A. A. (2020) "Pastoral Care and Counselling Intervention to Prescription Drug Addiction." *Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry AAMM*, 106.
- Adeola, A. A. (2021). "Prayer as a Toll for Wholistic Healing in Pastoral Care and Counselling." In Odunlami, E, Adeola, A. Ajedokun, F. and Ajeigbe, O. (Eds). *Perspectives to Ministering Care*. Lagos: Powerlinks Press and Publishers, pp.44–53.
- Afunlehin, M. O. (2019). *Overcoming Drug Addiction*. Oyo: The Blossom World Nigeria, 7-20.
- Alabi, M. & Adewole-Tambe, N. (2021). International Day against Drug Abuse: Nigeria Faces Harder Times over Rising Drug Use. *Premium Times*. <https://premiumtimesng.com> Accessed February, 2026
- American Psychiatric Association. "Causes of Addiction" *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, Fifth Edition. Arlington, Virginia. 2017, p 483–486.
- Ayankeye, S. O. (2013). *Counselling Practicum: A Handbook for Christian Counsellors*. Ibadan: Baptist Press (Nig.) Ltd.
- Benzio, K (2021). "How Does the Bible Define Alcohol Addiction?" <https://lighthouse.network/or/resources/addictions/alcohol-rehab>
- Cleveland Clinic. (2023). "Addiction: What It Is, Causes, Symptoms, Types and Treatment." <https://my.clevelandclinic.org> Accessed February, 2026.
- Eddy, E. A. (1965). "Drug Dependence" in A. F. A. Folawiyo, *Drug Education for Schools and Colleges*. Ikeja: Joja Press Limited.
- Enyioha, Ben U. and Ogundipe, Stephen O. "Crisis Intervention Ministry" in Emiola Nihinlola, Samuel Akintola, Ijaola Adelokoji (eds). *The Minister's Manual*. Ibadan: Baptist Press (Nig.) Limited, pp.122-127
- Fareo, D. O. (2012). "Drug Abuse among Nigerian Adolescents: Strategies for Counselling." *The Journal of International Social Research*, (20), 1-7.
- Greenfield, N. David (2018) "Youth Internet Habits and Mental Health" www.sciencedirect.com Accessed February, 2026.

- Kurtz, E. & Katherine K. (1992). *The Spirituality of Imperfection: Storytelling and the Search for Meaning*. Bantam Books. New York.
- Madoghwe, D. O. E. (2025). "The Gospel Minister and His Relationships" in Ayenkey S. O. and Amoran, O. S. (Eds). *Ministry Enrichment Series*, Vol. 12. Osogbo: Hirise Celebrity Publishers.
- Miller, W. R., & Carroll, K. M. (2011). (Eds.). "Rethinking Substance Abuse: What the Science Shows, and What We Should Do About It." Guilford Press.
- Morh, W. K. & Tasman, A. (2011). *Fundamentals of Psychology*. West Sussex, UK: John Wiley & Sons Ltd, Publication.
- Murray, E. & Hampton, D. (2025). *How Growing Up with Alcoholic Parents Affects Children*. <https://www.addictioncenter.com> Accessed February, 2026.
- National Institute of Drug Abuse (2017). "Drugs, Brains, and Behaviour: The Science of Addiction." <https://www.nida.nih.gov> Accessed January, 2026.
- National Institute of Drug Abuse (2020). "Drug Misuse and Addiction" <https://www.nida.nih.gov>
- Ogundipe, S. O. (2014). *Pastoral Perspectives on Caring and Counselling for Human & Sustainable Nature*. Gbagada: Danobish Creative Print.
- Oladapo Abel Oluwaseun (2023). "Aaron Beck's Cognitive Behavioral Therapy as a Remedy for Drug Addiction among University Students in Oyo State Nigeria." *A Dissertation in the Department of Practical Theology*, NBTS. Ogbomoso.
- Oyedele, Sam. O. (2001). *Principle and Practice of Pastoral Care and Counselling, Resource for Effective Pastoral Ministry*. Ogbomoso. Samak Press and Publishers.
- Gyang D. Pam. (2001) *Alcoholism, Drunkenness, and Drug Addiction: The Remedy*. Jos: Sele Printing and Publishing House.
- Premium Times (2021) "Intl. Day against Drug Abuse: Nigeria Faces Harder Times over Rising Drug Use." www.premiumtimes.ng.com Accessed December, 2025.
- Rogers, C. R. (1957). "The Necessity and Sufficient Conditions for Therapeutic Personality Change." *Journal of Consulting Psychology*. Vol. 21, p. 95–103.
- Shaffer, H. J., LaPlante, D. A., LaBrie, R. A., Kidman, R. C., Donato, A. N., & Stanton, M. V. (2004). Toward a Syndrome Model of Addiction: Multiple Expressions, Common Etiology." *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 12(6), 367–374.
- University of Pittsburgh Medical Center (2025). "Substance Abuse Types, Diagnosis, and Treatment." *Life Changing Medicine* <https://www.upmc.com>.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2018). *World Drug Report 2018*. Austria: United Nations Publication, <https://www.unodc.org/wdr2018> Accessed March 2026.

-
- Research Gate (2023). "Prevalence of Drug Use in Nigeria by Geopolitical Zones and States, 2017." www.researchgate.net Accessed January, 2026.
- Volkow, N. D., & Koob, G. (2015). "Brain Disease Model of Addiction: Why Is It So Controversial?" *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 2(8), pp. 677-679
- Volkow, N. D., Jones, E. B., Einstein, E. B., & Wargo, E. M. (2019). "Prevention and Treatment of Opioid Misuse and Addiction." *JAMA Psychiatry*, 76, (2), pp. 208–216.
- World Health Organization. (2018). *Global Status Report on Alcohol and Health 2018*.
- World Health Organization. 2021) Alcohol <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheet/detail/alcohol>. Accessed January, 2026.